

The Ultimate RDM Baking Guide

Recipes for FAIR
Deliciousness

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About this book

This book is for you if you have always wanted to know what is going on behind the scenes when researchers are creating their mouthwatering desserts. It will take you on a journey through the art of FAIR baking with its collection of carefully curated recipes. By picking up this book, you are already one step closer to becoming an RDM baker.

RDM baking is about much more than the final cake. The ingredients are just as valuable and deserving of the spotlight. Together they comprise the final creation that you want to share with the world.

This book will teach you the fundamentals that are the backbone of any RDM recipe and breaks down the process into easily manageable steps.

I hope that this book will inspire you to create delicious desserts and help you adapt your own unique recipes.

Happy baking!

Why should you care about this book?

External incentives

Financial accountability: Good ingredients can be quite expensive. If someone is willing to fund your baking endeavors, they will want transparency in how their investment is used, not only for the final product, but also during and after the process.

Showcasing your creation: Choosing a journal platform for your cake is a great way to show off your creation. Depending on your choice, stipulations might be in place demanding that you also show off your ingredients in a way others are able to understand and reuse them.

Compliance with policies and laws: Rules dictate how certain ingredients are processed and stored. If you collect those ingredients, you must show that you adhere to them.

Community acceptance: The baking community will receive your creation more favorably if they believe that it was created to the highest standards and can be reproduced. This might lead to collaborative opportunities with other bakers.

Ethical obligations: Good management ensures that you treat your ingredients with respect at every stage, fulfilling your ethical responsibilities.

Benefits for you

Efficiency: Thorough planning makes the baking process faster and more efficient. Investing time and energy in keeping your workspace well organized will make it easier to find what you need, will prevent loss of ingredients, and reduce duplication of efforts. It will save you time that is otherwise lost in searching for, recovering, and deciphering ingredients.

Trustworthiness: Documenting the process well enough that others can replicate it helps to make sure that the recipe is foolproof and makes your creation more trustworthy.

Continuity: Good documentation makes sure that you and others know how to continue from where you left off if you have to take a break from the process.

Error reduction: Investing the effort in good management helps to reduce errors such as forgetting to check the quality of your ingredients. It also helps you mitigate the risk of your ingredients getting stolen or becoming corrupted and allows you to be more confident in the security of your ingredients and the taste of your cake.

Benefits for the Community

Waste reduction: Good management helps reduce waste and contributes to a cleaner environment by preventing ingredient spoilage.

Recycling Opportunities: Properly managed ingredients can be reused, promoting sustainability. When others want to use your ingredients, they can easily find and trust their quality, ultimately contributing to a world with more delicious baked goods.

Innovation: Others might come up with unique ideas to use your ingredients, fostering innovation in the baking community.

So, what is stopping you?

At this point, you might still not be convinced about the usefulness of this book. Maybe you think keeping a tidy workplace is a good idea, but you don't see the value of sharing your ingredients.

We have collected some common objections to RDM baking with the hope of dispelling any remaining doubts.

“I don't have the time for this, I'll just deal with it as I go.”

Time is a common concern among bakers. It might seem like a hassle, but starting early with planning your baking process will help you save time and effort down the road. If you have a clear plan of how you will organize your ingredients and proceed with your steps, you avoid potential mistakes and last-minute scrambling.

“It is not a priority.”

Good ingredient management is increasingly becoming a priority, especially if you need funding. Funding bodies require transparency in how their investment is used and adopting these practices early on can open doors to financial support, helping you achieve your baking goals more efficiently.

“It is too expensive.”

Budgeting constraints are real, but effective ingredient management does not have to be expensive. You can get help with funding your ingredients and careful planning will help you avoid errors that can otherwise lead to additional costs. The budgeting tips in this book will offer advice on managing costs while still maintaining high standards.

“There is not enough incentive to share ingredients.”

It might not seem immediately rewarding, but you can get recognition from sharing your ingredients in the same way you get from sharing your cake. The recognition you get from the quality and care to put into managing your ingredients can lead to new opportunities and collaborations with baking colleagues.

“There are no consequences if I do not share my ingredients.”

You run the risk of being outed as a bad baker by your community. Refusing to share your ingredients can reduce trust in your methods, which can harm your reputation and limit your opportunities for collaborations.

“My ingredients will be misrepresented by others.”

Through good documentation and context, you can minimize the risk of others misunderstanding and misrepresenting your ingredients. It is in your power to help others understand the proper use of your ingredients.

“My ingredients are low quality, and I am too embarrassed.”

This is a common experience for many bakers. Everyone must start somewhere and feedback will help you improve to do better next time. Having others look at your ingredients and provide constructive criticism will help you identify areas of improvement in your baking skills.

“My ingredients are not very interesting or useful.”

You would be surprised at how valuable your ingredients can be to others. It is hard to anticipate what ingredients will be interesting for future bakers, but your ingredients might be exactly with another baker needs. By sharing, you contribute to a community where everyone can benefit from a wide variety of resources.

“I might still need my ingredients.”

If you are worried about needing your ingredients later, you can control access by putting a lock on your storage and setting a timer for when you're ready to share. Be careful not to overestimate for how long you want to keep them for yourself.

“I will lose control of my ingredients if I share them.”

You can choose a storage container that allows you to set limits on who can access your ingredients. It is also strongly encouraged that you attach a label to your ingredients that clearly declares how others can use them.

“If I share my ingredients, someone will be faster to create the cake.”

You can temporarily lock your ingredients up, if you think this is an issue. Remember that you have the advantage of understanding your ingredients best. Additionally, by sharing your ingredients you are already establishing that you were here first. Others will have to give you credit for your contribution, which will ultimately benefit you.

“I am not sure the ingredients belong to me. I’m unsure if I have the right to share them”

This is a common concern, especially when you borrowed some ingredients from elsewhere. It is important to identify this right at the beginning of the process, so you can be confident about what you can share without legal issues.

“My ingredients are too sensitive to share.”

Sensitive ingredients require careful handling throughout the whole process. Sharing is possible with the right safeguards in place. If full sharing is not feasible, you should at least provide the nutritional information of your cake and your ingredients. This way, others will know how your ingredients might be accessed.

“I’ll share the ingredients on request.”

Handling multiple requests will make it more cumbersome for you and there’s also the risk of your ingredients rotting without careful storage. Depositing your ingredients in airtight containers in a trusted storage will keep your ingredients fresh and save you time because you don’t have to answer inquiries about access.

“I am not sure how to do it, there is no support.”

Then you have come to the right place!

The Standard RDM Recipe

The RDM baking process follows a sequence that can be roughly divided into 6-7 stages.

Planning and Preparation

Planning the process includes carefully selecting the ingredients and their proportions, considering how they work together to create your desired cake and how they will be managed during and beyond. The recipes in this book have done the heavy lifting for you, but planning becomes crucial if you wish to **create your own recipes**. This stage also includes preparations, such as pre-measuring ingredients, ensuring that you have all the necessary tools at hand, and greasing and preparing your baking pans.

Gathering the ingredients

The baking process starts with gathering the ingredients using various methods and techniques. The complexity and intricacies of this stage can vary depending on the type of cake.

Processing and storing

The raw ingredients usually require some form of processing to be palatable and to blend with other ingredients. This stage is also devoted to storing your ingredients in appropriate containers to ensure they remain fresh and usable while you are working.

Creating the cake

At this stage, ingredients are mixed to produce insights. Careful attention to detail is necessary to avoid over- or undermixing. It is key to understand how ingredients interact for the final product to take shape.

Preserving the ingredients

After the cake is done baking, ingredients need to be stored in a way that ensures their long-term preservation. This includes converting them to sustainable measures and selecting the right containers.

Decorating and sharing

The next step is to prepare the cake and the ingredients for sharing. This entails decorating the cake with access statements and links to the ingredients and choosing a suitable journal platform to display your creation for public consumption.

Transformation Tips (optional)

Finally, transformation tips can be added to highlight potential areas of reuse for the ingredients to make them more appealing for consumption.

Know-how for the RDM baker

Principles for managing your ingredients

The four guiding principles described in this section are intended to support the reuse of ingredients and are widely adopted in the baking community. You will encounter these FAIR principles throughout the book many times.

Findable

F

Anyone should be able to find the ingredients and their nutritional information. This can be accomplished by creating a unique identification for the ingredients and using trusted storage containers for long-term preservation.

Accessible

A

It should be clear how to access the ingredients and their nutritional information, including the specific steps to obtain them and who to ask for further information. In special cases, only the nutritional information can be accessible which is still a fulfillment of this principle.

Interoperable

I

Ingredients should be provided in common measurements that enable them to be integrated with other ingredients or used for other recipes. Ingredients should also be labeled using standardized terminology.

Reusable

R

Ingredients should be prepared and shared in a way that enables reuse by others, including thorough description, nutritional information, and clear labels stating how to best consume them.

Sharing your ingredients does not necessarily make them FAIR, because others might not understand them.

Making your ingredients FAIR does not mean they have to be open, because sometimes they are too sensitive to share.

So, what should you do?

“As open as possible as closed as necessary”

Share what you can with as detailed a description as possible, but legitimate reasons for not sharing the ingredients are acceptable.

Budgeting: How a good recipe will save you money

The RDM baking process can be quite expensive. Ingredients, storage containers, and tools need to be acquired. Depending on the recipe, ensuring quality, security, and adherence to legal and ethical guidelines can incur high costs.

These are some of the costs that cannot be changed, but the key to being frugal is to **avoid additional expenses through good planning**.

A good recipe will help you do this at every stage of the process:

- ✓ Helps you make sure your **workspace is ready** for collecting the ingredients to avoid additional costs (e.g. forgetting to ask for consent and having to contact the participants again for retrospective consent).
- ✓ Reminds you to **label all your ingredients** clearly and consistently to avoid scrambling to reidentify them later.
- ✓ Guides you on checking the **quality of your ingredients** as soon as you obtain them to avoid noticing that some of your ingredients were faulty later on when you have already mixed them up.
- ✓ Reminds you of **documentation at every step** to avoid having to write it up retrospectively and missing some details.
- ✓ Guides you on how to best report the **nutritional information** in your creation by sticking to a commonly acknowledged standard.
- ✓ Guides you on how to **organize** and **store** your ingredients to avoid spoilage or having them all over the place and being unable to find them when you need them.
- ✓ Guides you on sustainable **file formats** and open software to avoid having to convert files for sharing which could include additional costs for tools and quality control.
- ✓ Helps lay out all the necessary **processing steps**.
- ✓ Helps you plan **anonymization** before you collect the ingredients.
- ✓ Helps you consider **legal issues**, such as ownership, right from the beginning.

However, there are some costs the recipe cannot help you with.

- ✗ Obtaining existing ingredients: It can widely vary how much others will charge you for their ingredients.
- ✗ What storage solutions and tools are available to you. Your options may be limited and/or more expensive depending on your location.
- ✗ How long it will take for the different processing steps e.g. transcribing.

Types of ingredients

Ingredients come in all different shapes and sizes. This section will give you an overview of the most common ones.

- 👉 **Numeric** ingredients are the backbone of many recipes. They are usually expressed in digits from 1-9 and are perfect for performing calculations and creating statistics.
- 👉 **Textual** ingredients deepen the flavor and add rich information to any cake. They consist of letters, numbers, and special characters or symbols. They come in many varieties such as transcripts, notes, or articles.
- 👉 **Image** ingredients add sweetness to the cake. Drawings, graphs, photographs, and medical images each unfold different flavors, ranging from caramel-y to rich chocolate.
- 👉 **Audio** ingredients consist of recorded sound, including voice and music. They add a good dose of harmonious delight to any cake.
- 👉 **Video** ingredients are combinations of moving images and sound. They will keep the cake from drying out with their dynamic interplay of elements.
- 👉 **Geospatial** ingredients consist of coordinates and are popular for adding a sense of space and direction to every creation, resulting in a fluffy and airy texture.
- 👉 And many more! (software, code, algorithms, 3D models, musical scores, textual varieties and collections)

Converting between Ingredients

Different types of ingredients are expressed using various measurements. While there are usually multiple measurements available for the same type of ingredient, some of them are more **commonly used and preferred** within the community, usually due to their high availability for every baker. Other measurements often require specialized tools that are not as readily accessible.

Preferred measures are also more **sustainable**, because they ensure that the ingredients can be effectively worked with in the future, while specialized measurements might become obsolete.

On the next page you will find a **conversion table** that will help you navigate between measurements for some of the most common ingredients.

Note that not all measures can be converted 1:1. For example, PDF/A measures lose some of the functionalities of PDF measures. In such a case, it is advisable to provide **both** measures at the time of sharing.

Original Measure	Preferred Measure
Numeric Ingredients	
MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) PDF/A (.pdf)	Comma-separated values (.csv) OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods)
Textual Ingredients	
MS Word (.doc/.docx) Rich Text File (.rtf) PDF (.pdf)	PDF/A (.pdf) OpenDocument Text (.odt)
Image Ingredients	
JPEG (.jpg/.jpeg) PNG (.png) PDF/A, PDF (.pdf)	TIFF (.tif) DICOM (DCM)
Audio Ingredients	
MP3 (.mp3) Waveform audio format (.wav)	Free Lossless Audio Codec (.flac)
Video Ingredients	
MPEG-4 (.mp4) AVI (.avi)	Matroska (.mkv) Material Exchange Format (.mxf)
Geospatial Ingredients	
ESRI Shapefile (.shp/.shx/.dbf)	Geo-referenced TIFF (.tif) MapInfo Interchange Format (.mif)

Who do ingredients belong to?

You will often work with a bunch of different types of ingredients in your recipes, some of which you gathered yourself and some you borrowed from others. In both cases you need to think about **ownership** to make sure that others can reuse your ingredients and that you are able to reuse theirs.

Just the raw ingredients are usually not owned by anyone. However, it is a different story if you have arranged a set of ingredients in a unique and creative way or if you have invested substantial amounts of effort in collecting them.

If you have ownership of the ingredients, whether through the **unique arrangement** or the **collection effort**, you have a say in who gets to reuse or distribute them and how. Similarly, others get to decide how you can reuse their ingredients.

It can be quite tedious to ask for permission and keep track of what you are allowed to do with which ingredients. If others don't know what they are allowed to do with your ingredients, they are less likely to want to use them which will ultimately affect the visibility, recognition, and impact of your ingredients and your cake.

Licenses

Licenses are a type of cover for your ingredients (and for your cake) that **tell others what they can do with them**. The most popular type of licenses are the Creative Commons licenses, because they are very easy to use, flexible, and widely adopted.

Be aware that they only deal with ownership. **Sensitive ingredients** are a different matter altogether.

CC0 entails free reuse of your ingredients **without any restrictions**.

CC BY means that others are free to reuse your ingredients so long as they give you **credit** for them.

CC BY-SA means that other must give you credit and share the reused ingredients under the **same license** as the original ones.

CC BY-NC means that other must give you credit and are allowed to reuse your ingredients **only for noncommercial purposes**.

CC BY-NC-ND means that they must give you credit and are **not allowed to modify** the ingredients.

CC BY-NC-SA combines attribution, sharing of reused ingredients under the same license, and restriction to noncommercial use.

CC BY-NC-ND combines attribution, reuse of unmodified ingredients and restriction to noncommercial use.

Which license should you choose for your ingredients?

If you want to enable maximum reuse, you should **avoid** share-alike, non-commercial, and non-derivative licenses.

- The line between commercial and non-commercial is blurry. Businesses will not be able to sell your ingredients, but other bakers might also not be able to reuse and share them in their creations, because journal platforms can also qualify as businesses.
- Share-alike can create problems if you combine ingredients from various sources, each covered with different licenses.
- Restricting reuse to unmodified ingredients can make working with them difficult.

The best options for most ingredients are **CC BY or CC0 licenses**. The choice between those two ultimately depends on your goals.

- If you want to ensure that you get **credit** for your ingredients, you should choose CC BY, but be aware that there are scenarios in which this license can become a hurdle for reuse.
- Maximal **re-use** is guaranteed with CC0, and it is the default for a lot of containers, but you must trust that you will get appropriate credit.

Personal recommendation:

The baking world is very competitive, and you deserve the credit for your work. Go for **CC BY** wherever possible!

Both are NOT good choices when:

- ✗ Your ingredients are **sensitive**.
- ✗ You reuse some ingredients but have not asked for permission from the owner.
- ✗ You reuse ingredients and don't know who owns them and are unable to find out.
- ✗ You reuse ingredients that are CC BY SA licensed.

What should you do when your ingredients are sensitive?

More robust or bespoke licenses will be necessary. For example, **scientific use licenses** will ensure that your ingredients are only reused for the purpose of creating scientific cakes. You can also conclude specific **usage agreements** with bakers who wish to reuse your ingredients.

How to apply a license in practice

- Put the license cover directly on your storage container.
- Add the information to your nutritional label.
- Add the information to a ReadMe file.

Licensing for your cake

CC BY is the best choice when selecting a license for your cake.

A useful way to quickly see if you can reuse other bakers' ingredients are **Open Science Badges**. To get such a Badge, the ingredients must be provided under an open license.

Lawful Baking

Some ingredients are sensitive and require careful handling throughout the entire baking process and beyond. If you decide to tackle a recipe that contains such ingredients, you need to be aware of their sensitivity and what that means for you.

Depending on their **level of sensitivity**, they should be stored at different temperatures.

Low sensitivity – Room temperature

Low sensitivity ingredients can be stored at room temperature, because there is no risk of spoilage. They do not contain any identifying or sensitive information.

Moderate sensitivity – In the Fridge, locked

Moderate sensitivity ingredients need to be stored in a locked fridge, because they can spoil and adversely affect the ingredient sources if left outside or free to access. They may contain indirect identifying information or information that could lead to re-identification.

High sensitivity – In the Freezer, locked

High sensitivity ingredients need to be stored in a locked freezer, because they can lead to serious harm if left outside or free to access. These ingredients contain highly sensitive or private information.

Examples of sensitive ingredients:

- **Personal** ingredients – contain direct and indirect identifiers about the sources
- **Confidential** ingredients – contain proprietary or classified information about the sources
- **Biological** ingredients – may contain information about endangered sources

These ingredients have in common that they contain something that needs to be **protected** against unwanted disclosure, whether that may be due to legal or ethical reasons, personal privacy, or proprietary considerations.

If you are working with sensitive data, your local **institutional health inspection board** might want to take a look at the process. They are usually concerned with three **ethical principles**:

- ✓ Respect for the ingredient sources
- ✓ Beneficence – minimizing harm and maximizing good
- ✓ Justice – fair distribution of burdens and benefits

It is a good idea to have a look at their policies and procedures before you start a recipe, especially if you are unsure whether your ingredients are sensitive. They will also be able to provide you with further guidance.

Personal ingredients

The next section will take a closer look at handling personal ingredients. They are important in many recipes and there are a number of **rules** you need to follow when working with them.

These rules only apply if

- you process your ingredients in the **EU**, or
- you are outside of the EU and import ingredient from the EU.

When are ingredients personal and when are they not?

- If they are sprinkled with **direct identifiers**, they are definitely personal.
- If they are sprinkled with **indirect identifiers**, they are also personal.
- If they don't contain any direct or indirect identifiers, they are not personal.

Direct

Name
Address
Phone number
Email address
IP address
ID numbers
...

Indirect

Age
Gender
Occupation
Income
Date of birth
...

There is also a difference between personal ingredients and **special categories of personal ingredients** (e.g. ethnic origin or religious beliefs). The rules are stricter for the latter!

Golden Rules of Lawful Baking

1. Lawfulness, fairness and transparency

Inform your sources about what will happen with the ingredients they provide and follow up on that accordingly.

2. Purpose limitation

Don't process the ingredients further outside of what is specified in your recipe.

3. Ingredient minimization

Only collect the ingredients that are necessary for the purpose of creating the cake. Be prepared to justify why each ingredient is necessary.

4. Accuracy

Take necessary steps to ensure that the ingredients are accurate and up to date. Remove ingredients that are inaccurate or of poor quality.

5. Storage limitation

Don't store personal ingredients in a form that permits identification of the sources for longer than necessary for the purpose of creating the cake.

6. Integrity and confidentiality

Take necessary measures to ensure that the ingredients are processed safely, securely, and without unauthorized access or risk of accidental loss.

These rules seem a bit restrictive, right? You may wonder if you will be able to follow all of them.

Fortunately, there is a bit more leeway for you as an RDM baker!

You are allowed to further process personal ingredients for the purposes of **archiving, scientific, historical, and statistical baking purposes.**

This is not considered incompatible with the initial purpose, even though it may not have been expressly mentioned earlier, but you must still take care to

- ensure appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the ingredient sources,
- respect the data minimization rule, and
- make sure that the sources cannot be identified as soon as you no longer need that information for the purpose of your creation.

Choosing a lawful base flour

The first step of starting a recipe containing personal ingredients is choosing a base flour. The choice of flour will affect the processing of the ingredients but not the shape of the final cake.

Some of them are more common in RDM recipes and likely more accessible for you.

Common	Less Common
<p>Consent flour The most common flour for RDM recipes. It is ideal for gathering freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous agreement from the sources for processing personal ingredients. This flour often has a granular texture to allow for better control when incorporating it into different parts of the process.</p>	<p>Contract flour This type of flour should be used when the recipe calls for the performance of a contract between yourself and the ingredient source.</p>
<p>Public interest flour This type of flour should be used when the personal ingredients are necessary for creating a cake that is urgently needed by the public. Whether this flour is suitable usually must be decided on a cake-by-cake basis.</p>	<p>Compliance flour Use this type of flour when the recipe demands that you adhere to a legal obligation.</p>
<p>Legitimate interest flour This type of flour is flexible and can be used for a variety of recipes. You should mainly use it if your pursuit of creating the cake does not outweigh the rights and freedoms of the ingredient sources.</p>	<p>Vital interest flour This type of flour is often used when you need to protect the health or safety of the ingredient source.</p>

If you choose the consent flour, you also need to get matching **informed consent** baking sheets. They will ensure smooth processing by informing your sources about what is going to happen with the ingredients, how they will be safeguarded, and what benefits and risk can occur.

Once you have your flour, and potentially also your consent sheets, ready, you will have to think about how to deal with the **direct and indirect identifiers** contained within your ingredients.

The best strategy is to not gather any identifiers at all, but that might not always be realistic depending on the type of recipe.

You have two strategies you can use to deal with them. In both cases, you will pick out all the identifiers and remove or substitute them with general terms. They differ in what happens afterwards.

Anonymization

The identifiers will be **discarded completely** and can no longer be retrieved.

Pseudonymization

The identifiers will **NOT** be **discarded but retained** in a separate container for later use.

With anonymization you will not be able to reinsert the identifiers you picked out and therefore your ingredients are no longer sensitive. However, with pseudonymization the ingredients remain sensitive, because you will still be able to reinsert the identifiers and know which ingredient source they came from.

Sometimes it can be hard to see whether you managed to pick out all the identifiers. Indirect identifiers can be especially tricky, and every set of ingredients is unique. If you are not quite sure whether you will be successful, it is always better to be safe than sorry. Treat them as if they were sensitive and think about how you can secure and protect them well.

But once you get the hang of it and become familiar with the workflow of sensitive ingredient recipes, you will breeze right through it. **Baking with confidence is the goal!**

The RDM Bakers' Workspace

A clean and organized kitchen makes for more delicious creations. This section will guide you on some strategies and tips for keeping your workspace in order.

Labels

Good labels are essential to quickly identify what you stored in your containers. You can use a different labeling strategy for different types of ingredients, but make sure you choose a strategy you are comfortable with and will be able to consistently apply. A few best practice tips will help you with that:

- ✓ Make the label brief but meaningful
- ✓ Use hyphens or underscores to separate words
- ✓ Only use lower case letters or choose an existing naming convention (e.g. camel case)
- ✓ Pick a consistent indicator for versioning (or add a date)
- ✓ Number with leading zeros (01_, 02_) if the ingredients need to be processed in a sequential order
- ✓ Use abbreviations for common phrases (e.g. students = stu)
- ✓ Use YYYY-MM-DD for dates
- ✗ Don't make them too long
- ✗ Don't use spaces between words
- ✗ Don't use special characters
- ✗ Don't use personal identifiers in the labels

It is good practice to keep a document where you record your labeling strategy in case you forget!

raw ingredients 1.xlsx

date_project_ingredientType_tool.csv

Organizing your kitchen cabinet

It is not enough to label your storage containers; you also need to label and organize your kitchen cabinet. This will make it easier to quickly grab your ingredients when you need them.

- ✓ Consider a **hierarchical** organization structure that clearly corresponds to different sections of the recipe.
- ✓ Shelf labels should be **unique** and only as long as necessary. Avoid assigning the same or very similar labels to different shelves.
- ✓ Strike a **balance between a deep and a shallow structure**. Putting a lot of containers on one shelf will make it harder to reach the ones in the back, but if you disperse them among many shelves you may have to look around a lot.
- ✓ Make sure that you have enough shelves to be able to **lock** some of them to protect your sensitive ingredients.
- ✓ Attach a **ReadMe file** to the inside of the cabinet door describing the organization structure in case you need to look it up again.

Selecting Storage Containers

Storing your ingredients properly during the process and afterwards ensures that your work can be enjoyed to the fullest. The choice of storage containers is essential to preserve the quality of your ingredients, to prevent spoilage or loss, and to ensure the safety of your sensitive ingredients.

Short-term storage containers

These are the containers you will use while you are working on your cake.

When choosing these containers, there are some aspects you will need to think about:

- **Size:** how big should they be to ensure they can fit all your ingredients?
- **Accessibility:** how well will you be able to work with them?
- **Level of sensitivity** of your ingredients: will you be able to lock and secure the containers?
- **Costs:** what is your budget and how expensive are they?

Portable containers

- ✓ You can easily take them with you on the go, and they are usually not very expensive.
- ✗ They can easily get lost, damaged, or stolen, and they are not very robust. You also cannot create automatic backups and will have to do them manually.

Use these containers when you need a short-term solution for your **non-sensitive** ingredients. You can also put sensitive ingredients in, but you need to secure them well. Do regular checks to ensure that there are no cracks in the material.

Cloud containers

- ✓ You can do automatic backups and easily share your ingredients with others during the baking process.
- ✗ Not all of them are secure and you should look at the “Made In” label. They may not be suitable for your ingredients if they were made outside of the EU. The manufacturing company may claim the right to look at your ingredients and you may also lose your ingredients if the company goes out of business.

Use these containers when you need to share ingredients a lot with other bakers but inform yourself thoroughly about the manufacturing company and do not use this as your only solution. Be sure to use an encryption funnel when adding sensitive ingredients to these containers.

Local containers

- ✓ You have full control over your ingredients at one location and can protect them against unauthorized access.
- ✗ They can easily get lost, and you cannot share them very well with others.

These containers are similar to portable containers. You should use them when you need a short-term solution for your non-sensitive ingredients and mostly when you are working on your own. Take care to secure them, especially when adding sensitive ingredients.

Network containers

- ✓ You can easily share your ingredients and access them remotely. You can also do automatic backups.
- ✗ They can be quite expensive, and you need higher security precautions to prevent unauthorized access.

Use these containers when you need an easy way to share your ingredients. They are also suitable for sensitive ingredients with a proper security strategy.

The same containers can be made of different **materials** (e.g. optic or magnetic). Some of them degrade faster than others, e.g. through exposure to hot temperatures or lighting conditions, so you should also carefully select the material when choosing your storage containers.

Good practice tips for short-term storage:

- ✓ Always use at least **two containers** of **different materials**.
- ✓ **Change out your containers regularly**, at least every 2-5 years.
- ✓ Always keep the **raw ingredients in a separate container** from the other ingredients and only work with copies you created.
- ✓ Confirm the freshness of your ingredients by doing regular **integrity checks**.

Integrity magnifier

Specialized tools are available that allow you to see whether your ingredients were changed in any way or if the ingredients are the exact same in two different containers.

What does “backup” mean?

This word “backup” has popped up quite often now and you might be confused about its meaning. This is something that is **unique to the RDM baking process**. You can (and should!) create **copies** of your ingredients, isn't that amazing?

It is vital that you can create backups, because there are many scenarios that could lead to loss or damage of your ingredients. Degradation of containers is one of them, but you could also accidentally change your ingredients during the process in ways you are unable to reverse.

There's a simple rule of thumb for creating backups, also called the **3-2-1 rule**:

Keep at least **three** copies of your ingredients in **two** different types of storage containers made of different materials and keep **one** of those containers outside of your kitchen.

This rule is straightforward and easy to remember, but in practice you will need to think about some more aspects, such as:

- Do you want to back up your entire pantry every time or just a portion?
- How many backups do you want to create and how often?
- What size containers will you need for them and where will you store them?
- How long do you want to keep the backups and how will you dispose of them?
- How will you protect backups of sensitive ingredients?
- Do you have a contingency plan in case a loss of ingredients occurs?
- How will you check the integrity of the backups?

Raw ingredients are the backbone of any recipe. You might need to revisit them in their original state during the baking process, because of mistakes or accidental changes to them.

It is good practice to keep the original version of your raw ingredients in a **locked container separate from the copies of ingredients you are working with**. This way, you can always go back and correct any errors that might have occurred. Do not forget to check the integrity of your raw ingredients.

For **sensitive ingredients**, you will have to diverge from the 3-2-1 rule. You should only create the **minimal number of copies necessary** to prevent the risk of losing track of them. In that case you would only create one backup of the original raw ingredients, which you should encrypt and store securely.

Long-term storage containers

Also referred to as **repository** containers. These are the containers where your ingredients will be preserved optimally to maximize their shelf life.

As with short-term containers, you have different options for where you want to store your ingredients for the long-term. Be aware that the choice of container has an impact on the **reuse potential** of your ingredients.

Journal containers

- ✓ Your ingredients will be displayed right next to your cake, making them easily visible to other bakers.
- ✗ Once you put the ingredients in, they are no longer in your control. They may automatically be covered by a paywall lid and the manufacturing companies may claim ownership over them.
- ✗ They often do not offer the space for all your ingredients and they do not guarantee their long-term accessibility.

Institutional containers

- ✓ These types of containers are usually provided by your local bakery. They will fit all your ingredients and are not very expensive for you if you are employed there.
- ✓ They are reputable in the baking community, and you can also use them to promote your ingredients.
- ✗ They may not be designed in a way that ensures a sustainable storage life for your ingredients.
- ✗ They may not support standardized and thorough nutritional labels.

General containers

- ✓ They are designed in a way that makes your ingredients easy to find and navigate, which will appeal to a wide audience of bakers.
- ✓ They support the storage of ingredients from a wide variety of cake categories.
- ✗ You need to carefully scrutinize the manufacturers' provided details on features such as long-term preservation and ownership.
- ✗ You don't really have control over the quality of your ingredients once they are added.
- ✗ You are usually only able to add very minimal nutritional information, making it harder for others to understand and reuse your ingredients.

(Trusted) Domain containers

- ✓ They are designed to support the storage of ingredients from a very specific category of cake.
- ✓ They usually have enough space to fit all your ingredients.
- ✓ They often come with detailed guides on creating documentations and nutritional information labels.
- ✓ They usually give you control of your sensitive ingredients and may also handle reuse requests for you.

- ✗ They may be more expensive than the other containers.
- ✗ You may have a harder time finding one that fits your specific ingredients.

How should you go about choosing one?

1. Try to use a (trusted) domain container.
2. If there is none, use an institutional container.
3. If there is none, use a general container.

If you don't know where to start, try searching for a fitting one in a **catalogue of containers**. You should always be on the lookout for ones that have a **trustworthiness certification**.

What does it mean for a container to be certified as trustworthy?

- ✓ They are made of materials that do not degrade easily and include a warranty for the long-term preservation of your ingredients.
- ✓ They fit all different types of license covers.
- ✓ Their design reflects legal and ethical compliance for the category of cake the ingredients belong to.
- ✓ They have an integrated integrity magnifier that assures that your ingredients remain unchanged and uncorrupted from the moment you put them in.
- ✓ They have integrated quality assurance procedures to ensure other bakers of the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of your ingredients.
- ✓ Your ingredients will be fit with a unique identifier, and it will be clearly indicated to bakers how they should give you credit.
- ✓ They have a clear standard for the nutritional information labels including information about where to find the cake.

Some additional tips:

- Think about your long-term storage container early on during the process. It will take you less time to prepare your ingredients for the long-term storage containers if your memory about them is fresh.
- Consider promoting your ingredients via an ingredient paper in an ingredient journal, just as you would promote your cake.
- Consider getting expert help for preparing your ingredients for the long-term storage container by a staff member of the manufacturing company. This will help enhance the quality of your ingredients.

Access locks

Once you put your ingredients into one of the long-term storage containers, you can choose to secure it with an access lock. These smart locks will open if certain conditions are fulfilled.

Safeguard lock

This is your lock of choice when your ingredients are sensitive because they contain some indirect identifiers that may relate them to the ingredient sources. It will open for verified bakers who have registered on the repository container manufacturer's website.

Restriction lock

If your ingredients are highly sensitive and contain direct identifiers, this lock will protect them optimally. It will only open for verified bakers who have sought and received permission from the repository containers' manufacturer.

Embargo lock

Use this lock if you have plans to create another cake with your ingredients and want to keep them for yourself for a bit longer. The lock will open automatically after the timer you have set runs out.

If you choose to secure your containers with any of these locks, it is important that the **nutritional information** remains accessible to everyone who is interested in them!

If you choose not to apply any of these locks, other bakers who wish to access your ingredients do not need to be verified or registered. They are only bound by the license cover you chose.

Securing your kitchen

Whether a lot of people are going in and out of your kitchen or not, it is vital to secure and lock this area to ensure that only those you've granted permission can access your ingredients. This is crucial for **both sensitive and non-sensitive ingredients**, because you don't want anyone to mess with either of them, although your security for sensitive ingredients should be more stringent.

Invest in sturdy locks with strong **password** protection and use them for your kitchen doors, your cabinets, as well as the individual storage containers. Store the passwords in a sealed envelope in a secure nook of your kitchen or use a **password management system** to ensure you don't forget them.

Purchase qualitative **encryption** filters and funnels. They are a kitchen essential for protecting your ingredients, especially when you are transferring your ingredients into cloud containers or when you are moving your containers around a lot. These tools scramble your ingredients in a way that makes them no longer understandable by anyone, yourself included, without the proper **key**. The key is another tool that allows to your make sense of the ingredients again, so it is important that you do not lose it or give it away. Look for the pretty good privacy (PGP) certification when choosing these tools.

Tip: Some tools, such as spatulas or spoons, are available with built-in encryption filters, so you can forgo buying an extra tool.

To make your containers extra secure, grease them well with **antivirus software**, wrap them in **firewalls**, and cover them with **data access log lids**. The latter will automatically record who tried to get into the containers.

If you decide to let others access your sensitive ingredients, think about having them sign a **non-disclosure agreement**.

Never leave your containers open or unattended while you are working and do not send them to anyone else without proper protection.

Make sure to communicate all your security precautions to the ingredient sources!

Do not forget to securely **dispose** of your ingredients. Just throwing them away when you are done is not enough to ensure that they are really gone. Someone may be able to fish them out of the trash again. Instead, you should completely destroy them by burning them or by investing in a good shredding tool to hack them up.

Creating nutrition labels

Nutrition labels contain essential information about your ingredients and your cake, such as types, format, and subject, and make them easily understandable for other bakers and they will be able to judge whether they want to use them.

You should follow an established standard for creating these labels to make them easily comparable to other creations. One popular standard is **Dublin Core**, which is comprised of 15 essential elements, but there is a wide range of standards that have been created for particular categories of cake.

Below you can see an example of a nutrition label created with Dublin Core:

Nutrition Information per serving	
Title	Technical Tiramisu
Creator	Dr. Susan Smith
Subject	Machine learning
Description	Ingredients for a vanilla sponge cake with predictive model filling
Publisher	Bakery XY
Date	2024-07
Language	English
Format	CSV
Identifier	doi.org/xxx
Relation	doi.org/xxx
Source	doi.org/xxx
Type	Numeric ingredients
Coverage	Europe
Rights	CC-BY 4.0

The Recipes

Mental Health Muffin: your pets will love it too!

„This multi-layered dessert is a delectable exploration of the relationships individuals have with their pets. Each layer will deepen your understanding of how pet ownership influences mental health and wellbeing. The sweet taste of the potential for mental health interventions will leave you wanting more.”

Preparation time: 8 weeks

Baking time: 12 months

Recommended prerequisites:

- *Training in data protection*
- *Research ethics training*

Preparation

1 sheet of ethical approval
1 sheet of interview guides
30 consent forms
1 research notebook
Institutional policies for greasing

Think about adding a distress policy, see [FAQ](#)

For information on consent, see [FAQ](#).

Prepare the workspace.

For this recipe, you need to follow a few preparatory steps to ensure that your cake is of high quality.

1 Line your pan with a sheet of **ethical approval**. Generously grease the edges with **institutional policies**.

2 Lay out an **interview guide** sheet to ensure that the quality of collected ingredients is consistent.

3 Prepare 30 sets of **consent forms** and formulate an **information sheet** to ensure smooth collection and processing.

4 Prepare a **notebook** to help you document the process and the exact quantities of ingredients.

Base

1 remote interview bowl
1 in-person interview bowl
1 cup of online survey software, e.g. Qualtrics

Gather the ingredients.

Start with a **round of interviews** sprinkled with a dash of **survey**. This will help you familiarize yourself with the ingredients and will make sure they are warmed up for the next stage.

1 Grab the **in-person interview** bowl and the **remote interview** bowl. Add the **online survey software** to the remote interview bowl.

1 cup of sociodemographic questions
1 measure of pet attachment
1 measure of mental wellbeing
30 human participants
400 g consent flour

1 digital recorder spatula, encrypted
1 videoconferencing software spoon, e.g. Zoom

Rule 3: Ingredient minimization

Keep the collection of identifiers to a minimum.

1 smartphone bowl, password protected
1 messaging app, e.g. Telegram
Toothpicks for prompting

2 Fill both bowls with the prepared consent forms and the interview guide. Add all **survey ingredients**: the sociodemographic questions, the pet attachment measure and the mental wellbeing measure.

3 Add the participants to the bowl that best suits their preferences and sieve 200 g **consent flour** into each of the bowls.

4 For the in-person interview bowl, use the encrypted digital recorder spatula and stir well until **audio recordings** have formed. You will also see **paper files** of responses to the survey ingredients, as well as drawings and notes emerge. Record observations of the process in the notebook and set the bowl aside.

5 For the remote interview bowl, use the videoconferencing software spoon and mix well until **audio, video, and text files** have formed. Take notes of the process in the notebook and set the bowl aside.

Now it is time to continue with the **diary study**. This stage requires some patience, but the in-depth insight into participants' experiences you will collect is completely worth it.

6 Take the **password protected smartphone** bowl and add a **messaging app** of your choice. This will be your way of collecting the entries.

7 Add the participants in again and blend well to form a smooth dough. Cover the dough and let it rise over a few weeks. Prick the dough with a toothpick daily to prompt participants, ensuring consistent diary entries.

8 You should see 5-10 diary entries per participant per day form, either as text or audio, capturing their daily interactions with their pets and their affective states.

9 Once the dough has risen above the bowl, remove the cover and set aside.

Ingredients collected during the final **exit survey** stage will act as binding agents that help create a cohesive picture of how the interview and diary study experience was perceived by the participants.

1 cup of exit questions

Tip: Inform your ingredient sources about mental health support resources to ensure a safe exit from the process.

Store

A heap of anonymous Identifiers
1 code key sheet

Tip: Use the automatic anonymization feature, if available, when taking the files out of the online survey software bowl.

1 kitchen cabinet, locked

2 institutional network containers, locked

10 Take the online survey software again and add it to a bowl together with a cup of exit questions.

11 Carefully fold the participant back in to get an impression about how the process has impacted their wellbeing and set aside.

Organize and Store.

You now have bowls containing a variety of physical and digital files. Clear structure and secure storage are key for keeping them fresh for further processing.

1 Take the files out of all bowls. Rename them with **anonymous identifiers** and fill out a **code key sheet** so you know which participants the files developed from.

2 Thoroughly **clean the bowls and tools** to make sure that no trace of the files remains.

3 Delete the video files. You no longer need them.

4 Scan all the paper files from the in-person interview bowl, as well as the entries in your notebook.

5 Put the original paper files in a locked cabinet in your kitchen. Make sure that no one else can open it without your approval.

6 Add all digital **consent forms and the code key files** to an **institutional network** container. Lock the container with a password and cover it with a **data privacy access log** lid.

7 Add the rest of the digitized paper files, the survey files, and all audio files to the **second institutional network container** and lock it with a password.

1 data privacy access log lid

Password-protect each individual file for extra security.

Process

1 transcription service bowl
1 file transfer encryption funnel

1 dash of general terms, if necessary

Complete anonymization will likely not be possible.

1 data privacy access log lid

8 Clearly **label** the containers and be consistent in your structure of organization to be able to quickly retrieve them. Look inside your storage daily to check for any changes.

Process the ingredients.

Now that your ingredients are organized, you need to process them before you can create the batter for your cake.

1 Transfer the audio files to the **transcription service** bowl, using the file transfer encryption funnel, and wait until transcripts emerge.

2 Take the transcripts out of the bowl and take some time to carefully check if they were processed correctly. Document any changes you make to the transcripts in your notebook.

3 Lay them out on your workspace and pick out any **identifying information**, including names of pets. You can either remove it completely or substitute it with a dash of general terms.

4 Repeat step 3 for the survey files, if necessary.

5 Add the **anonymized files** to the drive container with the digitized paper files, survey files, and audio files.

6 Also add the **raw transcripts** to the container but use a separate compartment and cover with another data privacy access log lid.

Taking stock

Well done! You should now have

- All your digital original and anonymized files in an access-restricted and password-protected drive container.
- All your files that allow re-identification in a separate access-restricted and password-protected drive container.
- All your paper files in a secure kitchen cabinet.

Bake

1 cup of statistical analysis software, e.g. SPSS

1 cup of qualitative content analysis software, e.g. NVivo

Document the qualitative coding frames.

Archive

1 domain container, trusted

1 teaspoon of unique identifier

1 scientific use license
1 safeguarded access lock

Bake the cake.

Now it is time to mix it all together.

1 Add the survey files and one cup of **statistical analysis software** to a bowl and mix until descriptive statistics have formed that give you information on participant demographics, rates of pet ownership, and mental wellbeing.

2 Add one cup of **qualitative analysis software** and the anonymized transcripts to another bowl. Add a pinch of researcher observations from your notebook. Mix well until you get an understanding of the influence of pet interactions over time.

3 Bake at 180 °C for 12 months or until you can identify approaches for mental health interventions. Set on a rack to cool.

Archive.

While your cake is cooling down, it is time to clean up your workspace.

1 Take the files containing **identifiable participant information**, the audio files, and the paper files out of your container and kitchen cabinet and **destroy** them.

2 Take the **anonymized files** and transfer them to the **trusted domain container** so that others can become aware of them.

3 Attach a nutritional label that describes the content of the files in great detail and add a unique **identifier** that makes your ingredients discoverable.

4 Cover with a **scientific use license** that restricts reuse of your sensitive ingredients to other RDM cakes and lock the container with **safeguarded access smart lock**. Verified bakers will be able to open the container via fingerprint

Keep for the retention period specified in your institutional guidelines.

Share

1 institutional container
1 open-access journal
A dash of data sharing info

Take care not to put any direct quotes into the publication or presentations.

6 Keep the digitized consent forms and all other **raw files** in the institutional network container. They will remain fresh there for a min. of 10 years.

Decorate and share the cake.

It is now time to share your cake and your ingredients with others.

1 Store information about your cake in the institutional repository container and create a link to the domain repository container containing the data.

2 Promote your ingredients through the domain repository container manufacturers email list of new sets of ingredients and advertise them on your baking website.

3 Present your cake at conferences and put it into an **open-access journal**. Be sure to include information about your ingredients and where they are stored to encourage reuse by interested bakers.

FAQ

My cake and ingredients turned out delicious, but I forgot to add in the consent forms, am I still allowed to share?

For your consent flour to be effective, you need to prove that your data sources actually consented to the process. If you forgot to add the consent forms at the beginning, you can still add them retrospectively after you are done. Be aware that there is a high possibility you will not be able to reach all the data sources again. In that case you will need to remove the ingredients from those data sources.

What do I need to include in a consent form?

Include everything that is necessary to ensure your ingredient sources are fully informed of what is expected of them, what will happen with the ingredients they provide, and how they will be protected. Include consent to share and store the ingredients long-term and also inform you sources about their right to withdraw.

Why would I need a distress policy?

Depending on the questions during the interview, for example targeting self-harm behavior, data sources might show signs of distress. Having a clear policy in place will help you react to such situations accordingly.

My data sources are all remote, do I still need the in-person interview bowl?

If your sources are all remote, you can leave the in-person bowl out and only work with the remote bowl.

Could I use different bowls for the interview data and the survey data?

Yes, you could use different bowls, but using the same bowl will make your life easier by saving time. You will also be able to confirm that you get responses from all ingredients sources which will prevent any air bubbles from forming in your dough.

Why do I have to use two network containers?

It is important to store the code keys and the research data in different locations to avoid easy reidentification. It allows to set different access restrictions for the different containers.

What if data sources no longer want the ingredients derived from them to be used?

They have the right to withdraw two weeks after interview and should be informed of that in the consent form. After then the ingredients will have been anonymized.

What does the Data Privacy Access Log do?

It helps you keep track of who obtained access to the sensitive ingredients.

Why is the scientific use license lid necessary?

To ensure that the sensitive ingredients remain protected and will only be used for the agree-upon purposes of creating scientific cakes. You can also use another bespoke license lid that offers adequate protection.

Why is the retention schedule for the raw ingredients necessary?

To prove the integrity of your cake. For example, it could be assumed that you fabricated some of your ingredients. You may also need a retention schedule if you made arrangements to inform data sources about the final cake.

What happens if I forget to dispose of the sensitive ingredients?

You could face heavy fines, warnings, reprimands or corrective orders. If it is necessary to keep them long term, be clear about that in your informed consent procedure.

Brown Bear Baumkuchen: a secondary data delight

“The Brown Bear Baumkuchen is a labor-intensive cake, but it is sure to impress anyone who is interested in how features of the landscape influence the movement and habitat selection of brown bears. The data collected from different regions in Europe give it a distinctive pattern. It offers an exciting opportunity to understand which areas are critical for maintaining connectivity of habitats and how conservations efforts can be planned to support wildlife movement and survival.”

Baking time: 2 years

Base

- 1 sachet of online search operators
- 1 literature management bowl
- 2 Excel bowls
- 1 spatial data analysis bowl
- 5 tablespoons of institutional regulations and policies

Gather the ingredients.

For this recipe, you need three different types of ingredients: literature ingredients, brown bear movement ingredients, and environmental and landscape ingredients.

1 Obtain the literature ingredients by using the online search operators to collect research articles and add them to the literature management bowl. Sift the articles into an Excel bowl to retain only the relevant results and set aside for further processing.

2 Download the environmental and landscape ingredients from open access platforms and add them to a spatial analysis bowl.

3 For the brown bear movement, you need to obtain access to a large spatial-temporal monitoring set of ingredients of three regions in Europe, which is stored in a domain repository bowl. This data is **sensitive**, so you need to request permission to access and use it. Check out the access locks on the container or contact the manufacturer. Once you have received access to the brown bear movement ingredients, add them to your second Excel bowl.

4 Generously sprinkle five tablespoons of **institutional regulations and policies** on top of your data bowls.

Rule 3: Ingredient minimization

Collect only the data specifically needed for this recipe.

Processing

1 spatial analysis bowl
2 cups of statistical analysis software

Process the ingredients.

Once you have gathered all your raw ingredients, you need to process them before you can create the batter.

1 Take the Excel bowl containing the brown bear movement ingredients and transfer it to a second spatial analysis bowl.

2 Add one cup of statistical analysis software and mix well to create maps of brown bear movement behavior.

3 Next, take the spatial analysis bowl containing the environmental and landscape ingredients. Add the second cup of statistical analysis software and mix well to create maps of the specific traits of each geographical context.

Once processed, you should have ~30 KB of generated codes and ~40,000 KB each of generated multiple maps.

Storage

1 institutional network container
1 institutional cloud container
1 private hard drive, encrypted
1 version-control tool, e.g. GitHub

Store the ingredients.

Processing of the ingredients takes some time, so you need to ensure that you have enough storage capacity while you are working.

1 The sensitive bear movement ingredients require special attention when storing to ensure they stay fresh. Pour them into an **institutional network container**, lock the container with a **password** and store in the fridge for up to two years.

2 Put the rest of the ingredients into the institutional **cloud-storage** and the **encrypted hard drive**.

3 Create **copies** of your ingredients and store them in a different location. Repeat this step periodically to ensure you can retrace your steps in case you lose some of the ingredients.

Do not forget to manage access to your kitchen.

For a label suggestion, see
FAQ

Include legends for the
maps

Bake

1 large cake pan

Archive

1 domain repository container
1 open access license, e.g.
CC-BY
1 unique identifier

4 Add your generated code to the **version-control tool**, to ensure that every change is well documented.

When storing the ingredients, be clear on your structure of **organizing** and **label** each of the containers to make retrieval easy. Create a **readme file** for a detailed overview.

Bake the cake.

1 Combine the processing outputs in a large bowl. Mix well until predictive biological models have formed that help you understand the movement behavior and habitat selection of brown bears.

2 Take the Excel bow containing the literature ingredients and slowly stir them until **insights** from previous cakes about human-bear interactions and the role of brown bears in ecosystems emerge.

3 Add the insights io the bowl containing the predictive models and mix until no lumps remain.

4 Pour the batter into a large cake pan and bake at 200 °C until you can identify **priority areas for species conservation over space and time**. Set aside to cool.

Archive.

Now that your cake is done, it is time to clean up your countertop.

1 Take the raw sensitive ingredients and all copies you created out of the storage containers and securely **dispose** of them by burning them.

2 Take the rest of the ingredients and processing results out of the institutional and personal containers and transfer them to a **trusted domain repository container** where the ingredients will have a minimum shelf life of 10 years.

3 Cover with an open access **license** to communicate how your ingredients should be reused. Attach a unique **identifier** to make your ingredients discoverable and include a citation suggestion. Finish with a **nutritional information label** describing the content of the container in detail.

Share

1 open access journal

Get creative in how you promote your creation!

The credit you can get from your ingredients and your cake will further your baking career.

Decorate and share the cake.

Once your ingredients are safely stored, the final step is to share your creation with the world.

1 Choose an **open-access journal** platform that seems like a good fit and display your cake there. Garnish with an ingredient **access statement** including a link to the domain repository container.

2 Promote your cake and ingredients at conferences and through your bakery's website.

Transformation Tips

Combine the ingredients with ingredients derived from the movement patterns of a different species in the region to create a layered cake of habitat sharing and interspecies interactions.

Feed the ingredients through a machine learning funnel to create a dynamic dessert that helps you predict changes in habitat selection given various scenarios.

FAQ:

Why is the bear data sensitive?

Endangered species location qualifies as sensitive data, because the welfare of the animals might be jeopardized. For a discussion of the potential misuse of animal tracking data, see Lennox et al. (2020).

Can I keep the ingredients in my fridge in case I want to make another cake?

No, you cannot keep them in your personal fridge, because they will not stay fresh longer than the specified two years. You can put an embargo lock on the domain repository container that will automatically open after a set period of time, but do not overestimate how many cakes you still want to create with the ingredients.

How should I label the ingredients?

Choose a style of labeling that is easy to understand and that you will be able to consistently follow. For example, a label for literature ingredients could look like this:

`publicationYear_author_title.pdf`

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Icons

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